

COMPOCASTING PROCESS OF GRAPHITE PARTICLE REINFORCED

Cu-10%Sn-10%Mn MMC

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ABSTRACT

Gr/Cu alloy composites might be much more considered in the electromechanical application field if the idea of composites is strongly adopted including the processing technique. As a economical and effective process, compocasting is tried to made high strength and low resistance Gr/Cu alloy compared with current powder metallurgy. With newly designed compocast system, the optimum process is obtained by experimental way with reasonable theoretical analysis. Compocast Gr/Cu-10%Sn-10%Mn MMC results in more than 5 times tensile strength and no less than 150% electrical conductivity of commercially available Gr/Cu alloy made by powder metallurgy.

Keywords : Compocasting, Tensile strength, Electrical conductivity, Optimum condition

1. Introduction.

In accordance with the complexity of materials required in the industrial fields, Metal Matrix Composite(MMC)s are coming to the front as new materials to satisfy these engineering needs. Even though many fibers and metals are considered as constituent materials in MMCs, it is very few for MMCs to make use of Cu alloy as a matrix material. However, Cu alloy which has high heat and electrical conductivity could not be disregarded with the low heat expansion coefficient graphite reinforcement for high conductivity, wear resistance and strength applications such as electro-discharge machining wire, electric motor brush, and semiconductor elements.

Currently, Gr/Cu alloy MMC is being produced by expensive powder metallurgy technique. However, the product is still having many defects like segregation and porosity. Compared with powder metallurgy technique or mechanical mixing, casting process is much cheaper and simpler. However, there are intrinsic problems in the composite manufacturing process by casting, which are poor wettability between reinforcement materials and matrix materials, and uneven distribution of reinforcement materials due to the buoyancy effect caused by the different densities.

In this study, compocasting process is taken to compensate for the problems occurred in the powder metallurgy processing of Gr/Cu alloy. Compocasting machine is designed to be appropriate for the purpose of obtaining the optimum process. The optimum process is studied by analyzing the influence of impeller shape and processing parameters on the dispersion of graphite particles in the matrix. Compocast Gr/Cu alloy specimens under different processing conditions are measured their mechanical and electrical properties and are compared with those of powder metallurgy processed specimens. The comparison shows tremendously bright possibility of compocast Gr/Cu alloy for high strength and conductivity applications.

2. Experimental Procedure

2.1 Compoasting Equipment

Fig.1 shows the schematic diagram of experimental apparatus and the shape of impeller used in this experiment. Experimental apparatus is consisted of stirring part, temperature controller part, graphite particle feeding part, and casting part. The stirring part is consisted of the motor which stir the melt, r.p.m meter which measure the stirring velocity, and height controller which move the impeller up and down. The temperature of the melt is measured by inserting the thermocouple into the hole in the middle of the impeller, and controlled by PID controller. The graphite feeding part is located at the top of the apparatus and connected to the crucible which feed graphite particles into the inside of the crucible. The casting part is located at the bottom of the furnace to pour the melt into water quenched mold. The shape of impeller chosen here is three types according to the effect of the melt flow during the sirring.

Fig. 1 The schematic diagram of experimental apparatus and the shape of impellers.

2.2. Optimum Manufacturing Process.

Experiment is performed to find the optimum process range for well distributed graphite in the matrix without defects. The approach is just try-and-error. Thus, the stirring temperature is referred to the solid-liquid state of the matrix. The stirring speed is decided to form the turbulent flow inside the crucible. The conditions considered in this study are listed in Table1.

	Stirring speed	Stirring time (min.)	Stirring Temperature (°C)
Constant	1020°C 8 min.	1030°C 900 r.p.m	900 r.p.m 8 min.
Variables	500	5	1000
	700	8	1010
	900	15	1030
	1100	20	1050

Table. 1 The stirring condition of experiment

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Effect of the Shape of Impeller

The aspects of the melt flow are examined by three types of impellers to know the aspects of the distribution of graphite particles in the melt. During the stirring, the flow of outer part is slower than that of inner part. Thus, the momentum of graphite particles in rotating center and in opposite side are different. The graphite particles are pushed to inner wall of the crucible because of the difference of the momentum. As the stirring rate is increased, the number of graphite particles which are pushed out becomes bigger and bigger. The graphite particles which are pushed out are raised to the surface due to the difference of the density between the particles and the matrix. The graphite particles raised to the surface are swept along in the center of impeller automatically because of the meniscus effect. Fig. 2 shows the degree of the distribution depend on the shape of the impeller under the condition of 900 rpm, 8 minutes stirring and 1020 °C stirring temperature. The shape of the impeller in Fig. 1 C shows the most excellent degree of graphite particle distribution.

Fig. 2 The effect of impeller shape on the microstructure

3.2 Optimum Compcasting Condition

It is understood that when the semi-solid state of the melt is stirred, the dendrites of the melt is strained and broken out to be solid spheroids. Therefore, the melt is becoming such a thixotropy state that the good fluidity and low viscosity state of the melt is helpful for the graphite particles to be fine dispersion. If the melt is being solidified with keeping this condition, the graphite particles are incorporated into the matrix by the network entrapping of the solid spheroids. To find this state of the graphite particles, many experiments are preformed by changing the shape of impellers, stirring speed, stirring time, and stirring temperature(Fig.3). According to the microstructure of each specimen made with different conditions, the processing condition of 900 rpm, 8 min, and 1010°C shows better than the other conditions. Higher stirring speed and longer sitting time brings larger solid spheroids due to the coalescence of the solid spheroids. In the case of the stirring temperature 1000°C, the fluidity of the melt is drop so that the graphite particles are not uniformly dispersed.

In Fig.4, the average size of the solid spheroids and the number of the graphite particles microscopically within $0.01 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$ are shown with respect to the stirring time(4A) and the stirring temperature(4B). The size of the solid spheroids is increased with the stirring time. However, the number of the graphite particle is increased with the stirring temperature over 1000°C.

500 r.p.m.

700 r.p.m.

900r.p.m.

1100r.p.m.

c) stirring speed(r.p.m.)

5min

10min

15min

20min

c) stirring time(min)

1050°C

1030°C

1010°C

1000°C

c) stirring temperature(°C)

Fig.3 The effect of stirring condition on the microstructure

Fig. 4 The size of solid spheroids and the number of incorporated graphite particles depending on stirring time (A) and stirring temperature (B)

3.3 Microstructure

In Fig.5, the microstructure of as-received specimen manufactured by powder metallurgy at Toyo Tanso Co. in Japan and compocast one produced by the optimum process are compared. Compocast specimen shows much better condition in the sense of segregation, defect, and dispersion. From this comparison, the mechanical properties of compocast Gr/Cu-alloy is expected higher value.

Fig.5 The microstructures of P.M. and Compocast specimens.

3.4 Mechanical Properties

Mechanical and electrical properties of specimens which are fabricated by P.M. and by compocasting are measured and compared through tensile test, wear test, and electrical conductivity test.

3.4.1 Tensile Test

Tensile test is done by a universal test machine of Instron at room temperature to 300°C . Fig.6 shows the shape and the size of specimens used in the test.

Fig.7 shows the tensile test result of P.M specimen and compocast one. The specimen produced by compocasting method shows much higher tensile strength than that of P.M. specimen. It is supposed that this aspect is not by the effect of inherent tensile strength of Cu-alloy, but by microstructural effect, that is to say, defects of the compocast specimen is less than those of P.M. specimen.

Fig. 6 The shape of tensile test specimen.

Fig. 8 The shape of wear test specimen.

3.4.2 Wear Test

Results of wear test under 0.382 m/sec friction velocity, 66.6 m friction distance, and 6.3 kg friction load are summarized in Table.2. Here, even though the volume fraction of compocast specimen is less than half of P.M specimen, compocast specimen shows much less amount of wear. Fig.8 shows the shape of wear test specimen.

	A partner disk radius	Wear traces size	Wear amount
Compoasting	14.74	2.21	0.1873
Power Metallurgy	14.73	4.09	1.1881

Table 2. The results of wear test under 0.382 m/sec friction velocity, 66.6 m friction distance, and 6.3 kg friction load

3.4.3 Electrical Conductivity

Electrical conductivity test is performed by four junction method at heating rate 50°C/min. From this simple method, the electrical conductivity of both P.M. and compocast specimen is obtained at different temperature as shown in Fig.10.

Fig. 7 The tensile strength of P.M. and compocast specimens

Fig. 9 The electrical conductivity of P.M. and compocast specimens

4. Conclusions

Gr/Cu-10wt%Mn-10wt%Sn composites are manufactured by compocasting and their optimum manufacturing process are obtained. Their mechanical and electrical properties are measured to show excellent compared with current commercially available composites. From this work, the following conclusions can be drawn :

1. In the limited selection, the shape of impeller is very critical for producing well dispersed graphite particle in Gr/Cu alloy composites.
2. The stirring temperature 1010°C, which in the solid-liquid state of the matrix material, gives the best condition of final product of Gr/Cu-alloy composites under 900 rpm and 8 min, stirring speed and time.
3. The electrical and mechanical properties of compocast Gr/Cu alloy is more than 5 times of powder metallurgy ones. It shows the strong possibility of replacing powder metallurgy method Gr/Cu composites to compocast ones with respect to the properties and the cost.

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